

Studies on the Dependence of Optical Rotatory Power on Chemical Constitution. Part XII. The Rotatory Dispersion of Stereoisomeric Anilino-, Toluidino- and Naphthylamino-methylenecamphors.

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In this communication we present new experimental data on the rotatory dispersion of the condensation products of oxymethylenecamphors (*d*, *l* and *dl*) with aromatic *monoamines*, namely, aniline, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, α - and β -naphthylamines.

α -Naphthylaminomethylenecamphors (*d*, *l* and *dl*) exist in two dimorphous forms. The higher melting form, in each case, is obtained direct by the condensation of the corresponding oxymethylenecamphor with α -naphthylamine. It is converted into the lower melting form by crystallisation from methyl alcohol with *prolonged digestion*. The rotatory dispersions of the two forms of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-enantiomers are identical (Tables XIX-XXX) which characterise them as dimorphous (Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 1007).

p-Toluidinomethylene-*d*-camphor melts at a lower temperature than that recorded by Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 359), but it has the same rotatory power as that recorded by Pope and Read (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 171). It appears that our lower melting form is a dimorphous modification of the one prepared by Claisen and his co-workers, but we have not been able to convert it into the higher melting form. Similarly anilinomethylene-*d*-camphor prepared by us melts at a lower temperature than that of Claisen and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). A similar explanation for the discrepancy based on polymorphism may be advanced, though in this case also we have not succeeded in obtaining the higher melting forms. The condensation products of *o*-toluidine with the oxymethylenecamphors are oils, which refused to crystallise.

The Influence of Chemical Constitution on the Character of Rotatory Dispersion.—Biot classified rotatory dispersions into two

groups, as they did, or did not, obey the laws of inverse squares. Recent work has shown that this law is generally not obeyed exactly, although some substances, such as sodium tartrate (Lowry and Austin, *Phil. Trans.*, 1922, [A], 222, 249) and the *dextro*- and *laevo*-forms of *p*-iodophenylacetylaminocamphor (Singh, Mallick, and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 95) obey it very nearly. Rotatory dispersions are however classified as "simple" or "complex", according as they can, or cannot, be expressed by the

equation, $[\alpha] = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$. Oxymethylenecamphors and their conden-

sation products with aromatic diamines (Singh and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 771; 1931, 8, 181) were found to obey the simple dispersion formula exactly. These compounds which contain 2 or 4 asymmetric carbon atoms respectively are complex ring compounds loaded with double bonds. It is now found that the rotatory dispersions of the *aryl* derivatives of aminomethylenecamphors now described, can also be expressed exactly by the one term equation of Drude. The nature of the solvent is found not to produce any change in the type of rotatory dispersion in this series, as is seen from the extensive measurements recorded in Tables I—XXXVI.

The value of λ_0 , the hypothetical absorption band in the ultra-violet, deduced from the dispersion equation, varies with the nature of the solvent, except for *p*-toluidinomethylenecamphor, the rotatory dispersion of which is expressed by the same equation in chloroform and pyridine (Tables XVI and XVIII). Its variation is of the same order as that of the rotatory power of the compound and the dielectric constant of the solvent in two cases, namely, anilino- and *p*-toluidinomethylenecamphor. In the remaining cases no such simple relationship can be traced, except that its value is lowest in benzene which has the lowest dielectric constant and gives the lowest rotatory power (Table A).

The Influence of Solvent on the Rotatory Power.—The specific rotatory power for mercury green line of the five compounds in different solvents are given in Table A. It is found that the order of decreasing rotatory power is methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol > acetone > pyridine > chloroform > benzene, except for α -naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in pyridine and chloroform and *m*-toluidinomethylenecamphor in acetone and ethyl alcohol in which cases the order is reversed (*cf.* Table A). The sequence of the dielectric

TABLE A.

(Specific rotations with reference to Hg_{5461} —line are recorded in this table).

Structural formula.	Solvent... Dielectric constant...	1*	2	3	4	5	6	Solvents in order of decreasing rotatory power.
		Benzene, 2.28	Chloroform, 5.2	Pyridine, 12.4	Acetone, 21.5	Ethyl alcohol, 25.8	Methyl alcohol, 31.2	
C_8H_{14}	[α]	367.1	424.6	433.2	448.9	451.3	480.0	6 > 5 > 4 > 3 > 2 > 1
	λ_0	0.3250	0.3360	0.3330	0.3359	0.3422	0.3425	
C_8H_{14}	[α]	352.6	384.8	405.8	442.3	439.9	454.4	6 > 4 > 5 > 3 > 2 > 1
	λ_0	0.3090	0.3467	0.3148	0.3347	0.3335	0.3366	
C_8H_{14}	[α]	355.4	401.6	401.6	425.8	440.8	465.0	6 > 5 > 4 > 3 > 2 > 1
	λ_0	0.3317	0.3356	0.3356	0.3365	0.3412	0.3555	
C_8H_{14}	[α]	361.8	393.0	389.7	418.3	423.0	430.0	6 > 5 > 4 > 2 > 3 > 1
	λ_0	0.3466	0.3445	0.3763	0.3718	0.3724	0.3738	
C_8H_{14}	[α]	331.3	388.6	398.6	417.1	428.0	445.7	6 > 5 > 4 > 3 > 2 > 1
	λ_0	0.3273	0.3439	0.3626	0.3463	0.3464	0.3324	
		Un† > $p > m$; $\alpha > \beta$	Un > $p > m$; $\alpha > \beta$	Un > $m > p$; $\beta > \alpha$	Un > $m > p$; $\alpha > \beta$	Un > $m > p$; $\beta > \alpha$	Un > $p > m$; $\beta > \alpha$	

* The numbers refer to the solvent as given against each at the head of the table.

† Unsubstituted anilino-compound.

constants of the solvents is also the same. The graphs of rotatory dispersion of *m*-toluidinomethylene-*d*-camphor (Fig. I) in different solvents, which do not intersect, show that the relationship holds for other wavelengths also. The same is the case for other compounds except for α -naphthylaminomethylenecamphor, the graphs of which for pyridine and chloroform intersect; so that the order for rotatory power given above is inverted for wave-lengths smaller than that for mercury green (*cf.* Tables XIX and XX, XXV and XXVI). The graphs for the remaining four compounds are not reproduced.

The Influence of Substituents on the Rotatory Power of the Position Isomerides.—It is seen from Table A that the sequence of the rotatory power of the position isomerides is, unsubstituted $>p>m$ in benzene, chloroform and methyl alcohol, whereas in the remaining three solvents the sequence becomes unsubstituted $>m>p$. This is neither in agreement with Frankland's lever-arm hypothesis (Frankland and Wharton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1583), nor with the electrostatic modification suggested by Rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1122). The unsubstituted compound has the highest rotatory power, but this is opposed to both the views. The change in the sequence of rotatory power with the nature of the solvent in the above mentioned instances, as well as in those of α - and β -naphthylaminomethylenecamphors (Table A) are also facts which cannot be accommodated on these hypotheses. These are brought out in a still more striking manner by comparing the graphs of rotatory dispersion of *m*- and *p*-toluidinomethylenecamphors in methyl alcohol, (Fig. I, graphs 6 and 7). It is seen that the *meta*- and *para*-isomerides intersect at wave-length corresponding to that of Na_D so that for wave-lengths smaller than $5893 \overset{\circ}{\text{A. U.}}$, the sequence is $p>m$, and for wave-lengths greater than $5893 \overset{\circ}{\text{A. U.}}$, it is reserved. Incidentally this brings out the importance of the study of rotatory dispersion in such investigations instead of deducing the effect of constitution on rotatory power from observations confined to a single wave-length (*cf.* Singh and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 774).

The Effect of Unsaturated Conjugation on Rotatory Power.—The *aryl* derivatives of aminomethylenecamphor from an intermediate series of compounds to the corresponding derivatives of imino- and amino-camphor, and are well suited for illustrating the effect of conjugated double bonds on rotatory power. A comparison

Rotatory Dispersion of m-Toluidinomethylene-d-camphor (1-6).

Fig. 1.

1—Benzene; 2—Chloroform; 3—Pyridine; 4—Ethyl alcohol; 5—Acetone;
6—Methyl alcohol.

of the structural formulae of the phenyl derivatives of the three series of compounds and the phenylhydrazone of camphorquinone and their rotatory power in chloroform brings out this effect in a striking manner:

(Singh, Mallick and Bhaduri, *loc. cit.*)

(Forster and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 947).

(Singh, Mallick and Bhaduri, *loc. cit.*).

This comparison brings out the enhanced effect on rotatory power of the phenyl group when acting in conjunction with the azethenoid group, and the remarkable fall in the value of the rotatory power when this conjugation is broken (1 and 4). When the phenyl group is not in proximity of the asymmetric centre but is divorced from it by the interposition of other groups so that the conjugation is broken, the rotatory power is also considerably depressed (1 and 2 ; 1 and 3). Lastly the above parallel shows that the auxorotatory effect of the carbon-carbon and carbon-nitrogen linkings is very nearly the same (2 and 3).

A similar relationship is revealed by the remaining four series of compounds.

The Physical Identity of Enantiomers.—According to Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, the *d* and *l* forms are represented as true mirror images of one another, differing in sign, but absolutely identical in the numerical value of the rotatory power. The numerical values of the rotatory power of the two forms (Tables I—XXXVI) further support this fundamental principle which has received ample proof of its validity in the previous parts of these investigations.

The individual readings of the angle of rotation did not differ from the mean by more than 0.02° . A calculation from the tables of rotatory dispersion will show that the maximum errors obtained by working out the effect on the result of the maximum deviation (0.02°) are generally well within the attainable limits of experimental accuracy.

Out of 297 observations of *dextro*- and *laevo*-rotations which are now recorded, only in the case of α -naphthylaminomethylene-*d*-camphor in ethyl alcohol for Hg_{5780} , the specific rotatory powers of the two optically active forms differ by 4.3° (Table XXIII) which corresponds to a difference of 0.035° in the observed angle of rotation, which is slightly greater than the maximum deviation (0.02°) allowed. The remaining three cases, in which the deviation in the observed angle of rotation corresponds to about 0.03° , are those of anilinomethylenecamphor in acetone for Hg_{4358} (Table V), α -naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in methyl alcohol for Cd_{5085} (Table XXVIII) and β -naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in pyridine for Ag_{5209} (Table XXIII). Besides the four cases mentioned above, there are only about ten other instances in which the differences correspond to variations in the observed angle of rotation lying between 0.02° and 0.03° . In all other cases this variation is less than 0.02° . All these are, however, of the nature of casual experimental errors.

The melting points of the racemic forms of *p*-toluidinomethylenecamphor and β -naphthylaminomethylenecamphor are higher than those of the optically active forms. These forms are true *dl*-compounds, at least in the solid state.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The *laevo*- and the *racemic* compounds described in the present paper were prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomers and had the same crystalline form and similar solubility.

Anilinomethylene-d-camphor was prepared by the method of Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*loc. cit.*) and has the same crystalline form but melts at $158-160^\circ$ instead of $167-170^\circ$. (Found: C, 79.84; H, 8.52; N, 5.57. $C_{17}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 80.00; H, 8.24; and N, 5.51 per cent.) *Anilinomethylene-l-camphor*, m. p. $158-160^\circ$. (Found: N, 5.51. $C_{17}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 5.51 per cent.) *Anilinomethylene-dl-camphor*, m. p. $135-136^\circ$. (Found: N, 5.58. $C_{17}H_{21}ON$ requires N, 5.51 per cent.)

m-Toluidinomethylene-d-camphor was prepared by mixing molecular proportions of oxymethylene-*d*-camphor in methyl alcohol and *m*-toluidine in glacial acetic acid and cooling the mixture in ice when a crystalline precipitate separated. It was crystallised from hot alcohol as colourless rectangular plates melting at 149-150°. (Found: C, 79.95; H, 8.73. $C_{18}H_{23}ON$ requires C, 80.30; H, 8.55 per cent.). It is fairly soluble in most of the organic solvents. *m-Toluidinomethylene-l-camphor*, m. p. 149-150°. (Found: N, 5.36. $C_{18}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 5.20 per cent.). *m-Toluidinomethylene-dl-camphor*, m. p. 120°. (Found: N, 5.26. $C_{18}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 5.20 per cent.)

p-Toluidinomethylene-d-camphor was prepared by the method of Claisen and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) and has the same crystalline form but melts at 179-180° instead of 183-189°. (Found: C, 80.16; H, 8.76; N, 5.34. $C_{18}H_{23}ON$ requires C, 80.30; H, 8.55; N, 5.20 per cent.). *p-Toluidinomethylene-l-camphor*, m. p. 179-180°. (Found: N, 5.34. $C_{18}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 5.20 per cent.)

p-Toluidinomethylene-dl-camphor, faintly yellow needles, m. p. 186°. (Found: N, 5.35. $C_{18}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 5.20 per cent.).

α-Naphthylaminomethylene-d-camphor exists in two dimorphous forms, *α*-form, m. p. 152°-154° and *β*-form, m. p. 76-78°.

α-Form: Oxymethylene-*d*-camphor (1.8 g.) dissolved in methyl alcohol was added to *α*-naphthylamine (1.6 g.) in glacial acetic acid and cooled in ice, when, on vigorous scratching, a pale yellow product separated. It was washed with methyl alcohol till free from acetic acid (yield 80%). It melts at 152-154°. (Found: C, 82.16; H, 7.80; N, 4.79. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires C, 82.56; H, 7.59; N, 4.59 per cent.). It is freely soluble in most of the organic solvents.

β-Form: On repeated crystallisation of the *α*-form from methyl alcohol, the *β*-form is obtained as pale yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 76-78°. The melting point of oxymethylenecamphor is depressed by the *β*-form while that of a mixture of the *α*- and *β*-forms is intermediate between the two. All attempts to convert the *β*-form into the *α*-form have failed. The conversion of the *α*-form to the *β*-form is accelerated by crystallisation from methyl alcohol with *prolonged digestion*. The presence of water is undesirable as it converts the product into an oil, which is very difficult to crystallise. (Found: C, 82.29; H, 7.80; N, 4.70. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires C, 82.56; H, 7.59; N, 4.59 per cent.).

α-Naphthylaminomethylene-l-camphor, *α-form*, m.p. 151-153°. (Found: N, 4.71. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.59 per cent.). *β-form*, m.p. 76-78°. (Found: N, 4.60. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.59 per cent.).

α-Naphthylaminomethylene-dl-camphor, *α-form*, m.p. 140°-142° (Found: C, 82.26; H, 7.77; N, 4.76. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires C, 82.56; H, 7.59; N, 4.59 per cent.). *β-form*, m.p. 88-90°. (Found: C, 82.24; H, 7.89; N, 4.74. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires C, 82.56; H, 7.59; N, 4.59 per cent.).

β-Naphthylaminomethylene-d-camphor was prepared in the same way as that of Pope and Read (*loc. cit.*) and has the same melting point (184-87°) and crystalline form. (Found: N, 4.77. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.59 per cent.). *β-Naphthylaminomethylene-l-camphor*, m.p. 184-87°. (Found: N, 4.74. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.59 per cent.). *β-Naphthylaminomethylene-dl-camphor*, m.p. 187-89°. (Found: N, 4.75. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.59 per cent.).

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2 dcm. jacketed tube at 35°. The value of λ_0 , calculated from the dispersion formula, is given in the tables and is expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

TABLE I.
Anilinomethylenecamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{70.71}{\lambda^2 - 0.1056}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3250.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4004	836.8°	-1.7°	Hg ₄₃₅₈	±838.5°	-0.6°	-837.9°	0.4016
0.4000	568.8	+2.2	Cd ₄₈₀₀	566.6	±0	566.6	0.4024
„	462.5	+0.7	Cd ₅₀₈₆	461.8	+0.4	462.2	„
„	427.5	+0.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	426.8	-0.6	426.2	„
0.4004	367.1	-0.1	Hg ₅₄₆₁	367.2	+1.3	368.5	0.4016
„	309.7	+0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	309.4	+0.6	310.0	„
„	292.2	-0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	292.6	-0.5	292.1	0.4040
„	264.8	-0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	264.9	±0	264.9	„
0.4000	228.8	-0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	228.9	-0.2	228.7	0.4024
0.4004	204.8	-0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	205.3	+0.1	205.4	0.4040

The solution exhibited mutarotation; the initial values $[\alpha]_{Hg_{5461}} = 367.1^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{Hg_{5780}} = 309.7^\circ$ changing to 341.0° and

287.2° in course of 3 hours and to 316.0° and 266.0° respectively in course of 21 hours.

TABLE II.
Anilinomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{81.21}{\lambda^2 - 0.1109}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3330.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4040	548.3°	-1.2°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	± 549.5°	+1.8°	-551.3°	0.4000
	507.4	+1.5	Ag ₅₂₀₉	505.9	-0.9	505.0	
	433.2	-0.4	Hg ₅₄₆₁	433.6	+0.2	433.8	
	363.9	± 0	Hg ₅₇₈₀	363.9	-0.1	363.8	
	342.9	-0.7	Na ₅₈₉₃	343.6	+0.2	343.8	
	310.6	+0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	310.3	-0.3	310.0	
	266.1	-1.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	267.5	+0.3	267.8	
	240.1	+0.6	Li ₆₇₀₈	239.5	+0.5	240.0	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE III.
Anilinomethylenecamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{81.83}{\lambda^2 - 0.1171}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3422.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4000	1126.3°	+2.3°	Hg ₄₃₅₈	± 1124°	-1.0°	-1123.0°	0.4024
	720.0	-2.1	Cd ₄₈₀₀	722.1	-1.5	720.6	
	579.9	+2.0	Cd ₅₀₈₆	577.9	+1.1	579.0	
	531.3	+0.6	Ag ₅₂₀₉	530.7	+1.1	531.8	
	451.3	-0.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	451.9	-0.9	451.0	
	377.5	+0.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	377.0	+0.8	377.8	
	353.8	-1.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	355.2	-1.1	354.1	
	320.0	-0.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	320.2	+0.4	320.6	
	276.3	+1.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	275.1	-0.5	274.6	
	245.6	-0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	245.8	+0.2	246.0	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE IV.
Anilinomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{78.57}{\lambda^2 - 0.1129}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3360.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4016	1023.0°	+2.0°	Hg ₄₃₅₈	±1021.0°	-1.0°	-1020.0°	0.4040
	536.7	-2.4	Cd ₅₀₈₆	539.1	-0.5	538.6	
	494.3	-1.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	496.1	+1.3	497.4	
	424.6	+0.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	424.0	+0.5	424.5	
	356.1	+0.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	355.2	±0	355.2	
	335.0	-0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	335.3	-1.1	334.2	
	302.6	±0	Li ₆₁₀₄	302.6	-0.6	302.0	
	260.3	-0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	260.5	+0.6	261.1	
	234.1	+1.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	233.1	+0.9	234.0	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE V.
Anilinomethylenecamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{83.08}{\lambda^2 - 0.1128} \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3359.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4032	1074.0°	-2.0°	Hg ₄₃₅₈	±1076.0	+1.8°	-1077.8°	0.4000
	704.5	-2.0	Cd ₄₈₀₀	706.5	-1.5	705.0	
	570.6	+1.0	Cd ₅₀₈₆	569.6	+0.4	570.0	
	525.9	+1.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	524.1	+0.9	525.0	
	448.9	+0.1	Hg ₅₄₆₁	448.1	-0.6	447.5	
	375.2	-0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	375.4	-0.4	375.0	
	353.5	-0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	354.3	+0.7	355.0	
	321.2	+1.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	319.8	-1.0	318.8	
	275.4	±0	Cd ₆₄₃₈	275.4	+0.9	276.3	
	245.5	-0.8	Li ₆₇₀₈	246.3	+0	246.3	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE VI.

Anilinomethylenecamphor in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{86.78}{\lambda^2 - 0.1173}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3425.$$

Dextro			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	Laevo		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4000	1197.5°	+2.5°	Hg ₄₃₅₈	±1195.0°	-1.0°	-1194.0°	0.4024
	765.0	-2.2	Cd ₄₈₀₀	767.2	-0.5	766.7	
	612.5	-1.3	Cd ₅₀₈₆	613.8	+1.3	615.1	
	565.0	+1.5	Ag ₅₂₀₉	563.5	+0.6	564.1	
	480.0	+0.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	479.7	-1.3	478.4	
	400.0	-0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	400.2	-0.1	400.1	
	376.3	-1.0	Na ₅₈₉₃	377.3	+0.5	377.8	
	340.0	+0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	339.9	+0.6	340.5	
	291.9	±0	Cd ₆₄₃₈	291.9	-1.2	290.7	
	261.3	+0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	260.8	+0.1	260.9	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE VII.

m-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.55}{\lambda^2 - 0.1202}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3467.$$

Dextro			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	Laevo		
Concn. g/100c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4016	493.1°	-1.8°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±494.9°	+0.4°	-495.3°	0.4028
	455.7	+2.1	Ag ₅₂₀₉	453.6	-0.5	453.1	
	384.8	-0.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	385.1	-0.2	384.9	
	320.2	-0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	320.5	+0.9	321.4	
	302.6	+0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	302.1	+0.8	302.9	
	271.5	-0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	271.6	+0.2	271.8	
	234.1	+1.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	233.0	+0.4	233.4	
	206.7	-1.1	Li ₆₇₀₈	207.8	-1.7	206.1	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE VIII.

m-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{71.37}{\lambda^2 - 0.0955}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3090.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α] =o'	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4028	436.9°	-0.4°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±437.3°	+0.9°	-438.2°	0.4016
	405.8	-0.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	406.0	-0.2	405.8	
	352.6	+0.5	Hg ₅₄₆₁	352.1	+0.6	352.7	
	299.2	+0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	299.0	-0.3	298.7	
	284.3	+0.7	Na ₅₈₉₃	283.6	+0.2	283.8	
	258.2	+0.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	257.5	-1.0	256.5	
	223.5	-0.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	223.8	+0.3	224.1	
	201.1	-0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	201.3	-0.8	200.5	

The solution exhibited mutarotation; the initial value [α] Hg₅₄₆₁ = 352.6° changing to 340.1° in course of 24 hours.

TABLE IX.

m-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{80.48}{\lambda^2 - 0.0991}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3148.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α] =o.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4016	503.0°	-1.2°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±504.2°	+1.7°	-505.9°	0.4022
	468.2	-0.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	467.4	-0.1	467.3	
	405.8	+1.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	404.2	+0.8	405.0	
	343.7	+1.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	342.5	+0.2	342.7	
	323.7	-0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	324.5	-1.7	322.8	
	296.3	+2.0	Li ₆₁₀₄	294.3	-0.2	294.1	
	255.3	+0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	255.2	+0.3	255.5	
	230.4	+1.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	229.4	-0.1	229.3	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE X.

m-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{82.31}{\lambda^2 - 0.1120} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3347.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4024	559.1°	-1.9°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	± 561.0°	-0.8°	-560.2°	0.4024
	515.6	-1.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	516.8	+1.2	518.0	
	442.3	+0.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	442.1	-0.1	442.0	
	372.5	+1.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	370.6	-0.8	369.8	
	348.2	-1.9	Na ₅₈₉₃	350.1	+1.1	351.0	
	315.6	-0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	315.9	+1.5	317.4	
	273.3	+1.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	272.1	+0.5	272.6	
	244.8	+1.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	243.6	+0.4	244.0	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XI.

m-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{85.21}{\lambda^2 - 0.1112} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3335.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4016	577.6°	± 0°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	± 577.6	+0.6	-578.2	0.4012
	532.9	+0.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	532.2	+1.2.	533.4	
	454.4	-1.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	455.7	-0.9	454.8	
	383.5	+1.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	382.3	+0.2	382.5	
	358.6	-2.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	361.2	+0.2	361.4	
	326.2	+0.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	326.0	-0.8	325.2	
	281.4	+0.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	281.0	+1.9	282.9	
	251.5	± 0	Li ₆₇₀₈	251.5	-1.0	250.5	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XII.

m-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{81.02}{\lambda^2 - 0.1134} \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3366.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4012	557.0°	-0.1	Cd ₅₀₈₅	± 557.1°	+1.7°	-558.8°	0.4000
	513.5	+0.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	512.7	-0.2	512.5	
	439.9	+1.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	438.7	+1.6	440.3	
	365.2	-1.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	367.0	-0.8	366.2	
	345.2	-1.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	346.5	+1.0	347.5	
	312.7	+0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	312.4	± 0	312.4	
	267.8	-1.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	268.9	-0.1	268.8	
	240.6	± 0	Li ₆₇₀₈	240.6	-0.6	240.0	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XIII.

p-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{80.13}{\lambda^2 - 0.1164}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3412.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4032	562.7°	-0.4°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	± 563.1°	-0.6°	-562.5°	0.4000
	519.2	+2.0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	517.2	+0.3	517.5	
	440.8	± 0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	440.8	-0.8	440.0	
	367.3	-0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	368.1	-0.6	367.5	
	349.8	+2.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	347.3	+1.5	348.8	
	311.3	-1.5	Li ₆₁₀₄	312.8	-0.3	312.5	
	269.0	+0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	268.8	-1.3	267.5	
	239.1	-1.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	240.1	+1.1	241.2	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE XIV.

p-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{79.56}{\lambda^2 - 0.1264}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3555.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100c.c.
0.4000	601.3°	±0°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±601.3°	-0.5°	-600.8°	0.4056
	550.0	+1.1	Ag ₅₂₀₉	548.9	-0.2	548.7	
	465.0	-0.9	Hg ₅₄₆₁	465.9	-0.4	465.5	
	385.0	+2.0	Hg ₅₇₈₀	383.0	+0.6	383.6	
	360.0	-0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	360.4	-0.5	359.9	
	322.5	-0.5	Li ₆₁₀₄	323.0	-0.2	322.8	
	276.3	+0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	276.1	+0.7	276.8	
	245.0	-0.9	Li ₆₇₀₈	245.9	-0.1	245.8	

The solution exhibited slight mutarotation; the initial values $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5461}} = 465.0^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5780}} = 385.0^\circ$ changing to 456.3° and 378.8° respectively in course of 15 hours.

TABLE XV.

p-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{78.77}{\lambda^2 - 0.1132}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3365.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c. c.
0.4016	540.4°	-1.0°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±541.4°	±0°	-541.4°	0.4036
	499.2	+1.0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	498.2	+1.0	499.2	
	425.8	±0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	425.8	+0.4	426.2	
	356.2	-0.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	356.7	-1.2	355.5	
	337.6	+1.0	Na ₅₈₉₃	336.6	+0.4	337.0	
	305.1	+1.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	303.7	-0.2	303.5	
	260.2	-1.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	261.4	-1.3	260.1	
	234.1	+0.1	Li ₆₇₀₈	234.0	+8.2	234.2	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation; but turned light pink on keeping.

TABLE XVI.

p-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.15}{\lambda^2 - 0.1126} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3356.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4008	505.4°	-2.1	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±507.5°	-1.7°	-505.8°	0.4040
	401.6	+2.1	Hg ₅₄₆₁	399.5	+0.2	399.7	
	335.5	+0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	334.7	-0.5	334.2	
	316.9	+1.0	Na ₅₈₉₃	315.9	-0.3	315.6	
	284.4	-0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	285.2	+0.7	285.9	
	247.0	+1.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	245.6	+0.7	246.3	
	218.3	-1.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	219.8	-0.7	219.1	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation but turned scarlet red in course of two hours.

TABLE XVII.

p-Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{66.65}{\lambda^2 - 0.1100} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3317.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4024	447.3°	-0.9°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±448.2°	+0.6°	-448.8°	0.4000
	411.2	-2.0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	413.2	-0.7	412.5	
	355.4	+1.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	354.1	-0.3	353.8	
	298.2	+0.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀	297.5	±0	297.5	
	280.8	-0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	281.1	+0.2	281.3	
	254.8	+1.0	Li ₆₁₀₄	253.8	-1.3	252.5	
	220.0	+1.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	218.9	+1.1	220.0	
	195.1	-0.9	Li ₆₇₀₈	196.0	-1.0	195.0	

The solution exhibited mutarotation, $[\alpha]_D = 280.8^\circ$ changing to 275° and to 250° in course of 1 hour and 15 hours respectively.

TABLE XVIII.

Toluidinomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.15}{\lambda^2 - 0.1126} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3556.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4008	505.4°	-2.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	± 507.5°	-0.5°	-507.0°	0.4024
„	467.8	+0.6	Ag ₅₂₀₉	467.2	+1.2	468.4	„
„	401.6	+2.1	Hg ₅₄₆₁	399.5	+0.5	400.0	„
„	335.5	+0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	334.7	+0.8	335.5	„
„	315.6	-0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	315.9	-0.3	315.6	„
„	284.4	-0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	285.2	+0.6	285.8	„
„	245.8	+0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₉	245.6	-0.1	245.5	„
„	218.3	-1.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	219.8	+0.2	220.0	„

The solution exhibited mutarotation, the initial values $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5461}} = 401.6^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5780}} = 335.5^\circ$ changing to 328.2° and 278.2° respectively in course of 30 hours.

TABLE XIX.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (α-Form) in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{70.45}{\lambda^2 - 0.1185} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3445.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4020	501.0°	-1.5°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	± 502.5°	± 0°	-502.5°	0.4020
	462.6	+1.4	Ag ₅₂₀₉	461.2	-0.2	461.4	
	393.0	-1.0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	392.0	+1.0	393.0	
	328.5	-1.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀	326.8	+1.7	328.5	
	307.1	+1.0	Na ₅₈₉₃	308.1	-0.3	308.4	
	278.6	+1.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	277.3	+2.5	279.8	
	237.9	+0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	238.0	+0.7	238.7	
	212.7	-0.1	Li ₆₇₀₈	212.6	+1.3	213.9	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XX.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (α-Form) in Pyridine

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{61.28}{\lambda^2 - 0.1416} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3763.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4004	522.0°	-0.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±522.1°	+0.9°	-523.0°	0.4008
—	—	—	Ag ₅₂₀₉	472.3	+1.8	470.5	
389.7	-1.7	-1.7	Hg ₅₄₆₁	391.4	+0.6	392.0	
388.4	+1.0	+1.0	Ag ₅₄₆₉	389.4	—	—	
317.2	-1.3	-1.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	318.5	+1.0	319.5	
299.7	+1.5	+1.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	298.2	+1.4	299.6	
266.0	+0.6	+0.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	265.4	+1.7	267.1	
224.9	-0.4	-0.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	224.5	+1.4	225.9	
198.6	-0.1	-0.1	Li ₆₇₀₈	198.7	-0.2	198.5	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XXI.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (α-Form) in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{64.78}{\lambda^2 - 0.1201} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3465.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4008	469.1°	-0.3°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±469.4°	-0.5°	-468.9°	0.4020
	428.4	±0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	428.4	-1.4	426.6	
	361.8	-1.9	Hg ₅₄₆₁	363.7	-0.6	363.1	
	359.3	-1.8	Ag ₅₄₆₉	361.1	...	...	
	305.1	+1.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	303.5	+2.4	305.9	
	288.2	+1.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	286.4	+2.1	288.5	
	257.1	+0.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	256.5	-0.2	256.3	
	217.4	-2.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	219.7	-0.8	218.9	
	197.2	+0.9	Li ₆₇₀₈	196.3	+1.4	197.7	

Mutarotation was observed after 24 hours ; the initial value $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}} = 361.8^\circ$ changing to 340.6°

TABLE XXII.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (α-Form) in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.41}{\lambda^2 - 0.1397} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3738.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c. c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4000	573.6°	-1.4°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±575.0°	+1.5°	-576.5°	0.4016
	522.5	+2.5	Ag ₅₀₂₉	520.0	+1.7	521.7	
	430.0	-1.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	431.6	-0.8	430.8	
	353.7	+1.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀	352.0	+0.4	352.4	
	332.5	+2.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	330.0	+1.2	331.2	
	290.0	-2.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	292.1	-0.7	291.4	
	248.8	-0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	248.9	+0.1	249.0	
	220.0	+0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	220.5	-1.1	220.4	

No mutarotation was observed even after 20 hours.

TABLE XXIII.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (α-Form) in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{67.74}{\lambda^2 - 0.1387} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3724.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4008	563.9°	+0.6°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±563.3°	+1.7°	-565.0	0.4000
„	512.7	+1.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	511.0	-1.0	510.0	
„	423.0	-1.7	Hg ₅₄₆₁	424.7	-0.9	423.8	
„	420.5	-2.2	Ag ₅₄₆₉	422.7	—	—	
„	349.3	+2.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	346.7	-1.7	345.0	
„	322.8	-2.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	325.1	-2.6	322.5	
„	292.0	+2.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	289.6	+0.4	290.0	
„	245.8	+0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	245.6	+1.9	247.5	
„	217.1	-0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	217.6	+1.2	218.7	

No mutrotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XXIV.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (α-Form) in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{67.05}{\lambda^2 - 0.1382} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3717.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4016	556.5°	-1.3°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±557.8°	+0.6°	-558.4°	0.4012
	505.5	+1.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	503.7	+1.1	504.8	
	418.3	-0.8	Hg ₅₄₆₁	419.1	+0.9	420.0	
	341.2	-1.1	Hg ₅₇₈₀	342.3	-0.8	341.5	
	322.5	+1.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	321.0	+0.5	321.5	
	285.1	-0.9	Li ₆₁₀₄	286.0	-1.9	284.1	
	241.5	-1.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	242.7	+0.3	243.0	
	215.4	+0.3	Li ₆₇₀₈	215.5	-1.2	214.3	

As the solution turns dark red on keeping it was not possible to examine the same for mutarotation.

TABLE XXV.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (β-Form) in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{71.94}{\lambda^2 - 0.1161} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3407.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4020	502.5°	-2.0°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±504.5°	-0.8°	-503.7°	0.4000
	465.3	+1.9	Ag ₅₂₀₉	463.4	+1.5	464.9	
	398.2	+2.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	396.0	+1.4	397.4	
	330.9	+0.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	330.0	±0	330.0	
	310.9	-0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	311.3	-1.3	310.0	
	279.8	-0.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	280.4	-1.6	278.8	
	242.5	+1.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	241.4	-0.1	241.3	
	215.1	-0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	215.5	-0.5	215.0	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XXVI.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (β-Form) in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{61.94}{\lambda^2 - 0.1413} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3759.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4012	525.8°	-1.8°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±527.6°	-0.2°	-527.4°	0.4020
	478.2	+1.6	Ag ₅₂₀₉	476.6	-0.3	476.3	
	392.3	-2.5	Hg ₅₄₆₁	394.8	+0.7	395.5	
	319.0	-2.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	321.2	-0.3	320.9	
	300.3	-0.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	300.9	+0.1	301.0	
	266.7	-1.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	267.8	-1.7	266.1	
	228.1	+1.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	226.8	+0.3	227.6	
	199.3	-1.9	Li ₆₇₀₈	201.2	-0.9	200.3	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XXVII.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (β-Form) in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{65.70}{\lambda^2 - 0.1191} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3451.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4004	470.8°	-0.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±470.7°	+1.0°	-471.7°	0.4012
	430.8	-0.9	Ag ₅₂₀₉	431.7	+0.7	432.4	
	364.7	-2.0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	366.7	-1.5	365.2	
	304.7	-0.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	305.6	-0.2	305.4	
	289.7	+1.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	288.1	-0.2	287.9	
	257.3	-1.9	Li ₆₁₀₄	259.2	+0.1	259.3	
	221.1	-1.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	222.4	+0.7	223.1	
	198.6	±0	Li ₆₇₀₈	198.6	-0.8	199.4	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XXVIII.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (β-Form) in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.44}{\lambda^2 - 0.1404} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3747.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α] =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4008	576.4°	-2.2°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±578.6°	+1.4°	-580.0°	0.4000
	522.7	-0.4	Ag ₅₂₀₉	523.1	-1.8	521.3	
	432.9	-0.9	Hg ₅₄₆₁	433.8	-1.3	432.5	
	354.6	+1.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	353.3	-0.8	352.5	
	333.1	+1.9	Na ₅₈₉₃	331.2	+1.4	332.6	
	293.2	-1.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	294.8	+0.2	295.0	
	249.5	-0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	249.7	+0.3	250.0	
	222.1	+0.9	Li ₆₇₀₈	221.2	+0.1	221.3	

No mutarotation was observed even after 24 hours.

TABLE XXIX.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (β-Form) in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.13}{\lambda^2 - 0.1380} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3715.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α] =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4008	563.9°	-0.6°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±564.5°	+1.7°	-566.2°	0.4000
	512.7	+0.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	512.0	+0.5	512.5	
	423.0	-2.0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	425.0	±0	425.0	
	348.1	+0.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀	347.4	+0.1	347.5	
	323.2	-2.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	325.8	-2.0	323.8	
	292.0	+1.6	Li ₆₁₀₄	290.4	+0.9	291.3	
	247.1	+0.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	246.4	+1.1	247.5	
	218.3	±0	Li ₆₇₀₈	218.3	-0.8	217.5	

TABLE XXX.

α-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor (β-Form) in Acetone

$$[\alpha] \pm \frac{68.33}{\lambda^2 - 0.1354}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3680.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	<i>Laevo</i>			
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.		Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4012	554.6°	+0.4°	Cd ₅₀₈₅	±554.2°	±1.1°	-555.3°	0.4008
	503.8	+1.0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	502.8	±0	502.8	
	418.9	-0.9	Hg ₅₄₆₁	419.8	+0.7	420.5	
	342.7	-1.1	Hg ₅₇₈₀	343.8	+0.5	344.3	
	322.6	-0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	323.1	+1.1	324.4	
	286.6	-1.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	288.0	-0.2	288.2	
	244.3	-0.5	Cd ₆₄₃₈	244.8	-0.2	244.6	
	216.8	-0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	217.2	-0.1	217.1	

The solution turned dark red on keeping.

TABLE XXXI.

β-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{78.55}{\lambda^2 - 0.1145}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3324.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	<i>Laevo</i>			
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.		Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4008	546.5°	+1.3°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±545.2°	-1.5°	-543.7°	0.4000
	500.2	-0.9	Ag ₅₂₀₉	501.1	-1.1	500.0	
	428.0	+0.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	427.7	-0.2	427.5	
	356.9	-0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	357.7	-0.2	357.5	
	336.9	-0.9	Na ₅₈₉₃	337.8	-0.3	337.5	
	304.3	-0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	304.4	+0.6	305.0	
	234.6	+0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	234.2	-0.4	233.8	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE XXXII.

β-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{79.14}{\lambda^2 - 0.1200}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3464.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4028	571.1°	+0.5°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±570.6°	+0.7°	-571.3°	0.4000
	521.3	-1.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	523.0	-1.7	521.3	
	445.7	+1.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	444.1	+2.2	446.3	
	371.2	+1.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	369.7	+0.3	370.0	
	348.8	+0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	348.5	-1.0	347.5	
	314.1	-0.5	Li ₆₁₀₄	314.6	+0.4	315.0	
	268.1	-0.6	Cd ₆₄₃₈	268.7	-1.2	267.5	
	240.8	+1.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	239.8	+0.2	240.0	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE XXXIII.

β-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{66.76}{\lambda^2 - 0.1315}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3626.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concn. g/100 c.c.
0.4052	528.1°	+3.3°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±524.8°	+1.2°	-526.0°	0.4020
	479.9	+2.4	Ag ₅₂₀₉	477.5	-1.2	476.3	
	398.6	-1.9	Hg ₅₄₆₁	400.5	-1.3	399.2	
	329.5	±0	Hg ₅₇₈₀	329.5	-1.2	328.3	
	309.7	+0.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	309.6	±0	309.6	
	275.2	-1.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	276.9	+0.4	277.3	
	236.9	+1.0	Cd ₆₄₃₈	235.9	+0.4	236.3	
	209.7	+0.1	Li ₆₇₀₈	209.6	-0.7	208.9	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE XXXIV.

β-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.57}{\lambda^2 - 0.1199}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3463.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	<i>Laevo</i>			
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$			Calc. $[\alpha]$	Obs. $[\alpha]$		Concn. g/100 c.c.
	=o.	o-c.	=c.	o'-c.	=o'.		
0.4028	540.0°	+2.8°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	+537.2°	+1.6°	-538.8°	0.4000
	495.3	+2.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	492.6	+2.4	495.0	
	417.1	-1.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	418.3	-0.8	417.5	
	346.3	-1.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	348.1	-0.6	347.5	
	326.5	-1.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	328.3	+0.5	328.8	
	295.4	+0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	295.1	+1.2	296.3	
	225.9	±0	Li ₆₇₀₈	225.9	-0.9	225.0	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation,

TABLE XXXV.

β-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{69.66}{\lambda^2 - 0.1183}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3439.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	<i>Laevo</i>			
Concn. g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$			Calc. $[\alpha]$	Obs. $[\alpha]$		Concn. g/100 c.c.
	=o.	o-c.	=c.	o'-c.	=o'.		
0.4040	492.5°	-4.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±496.6°	-2.1°	-494.5°	0.4024
	455.4	+0.1	Ag ₅₂₀₉	455.3	+0.7	456.0	
	388.6	+1.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	387.4	+1.5	388.9	
	325.6	+2.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	322.8	+1.5	324.3	
	307.0	+2.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	304.5	+1.1	305.6	
	273.5	-0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	273.9	-0.6	273.3	
	235.2	±0	Cd ₆₄₃₈	235.2	—	—	
	210.4	+0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	210.0	-1.3	208.7	

The solution exhibited slight mutarotation, $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5461}} = 388.6^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5780}} = 325.6^\circ$ changing to 381.5° and 315.6° respectively in course of 24 hours.

TABLE XXXVI.

β-Naphthylaminomethylenecamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{63.14}{\lambda^2 - 0.1071}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3273.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$	<i>Laevé</i>		
Concn.	Obs. $[\alpha]$				Obs. $[\alpha]$	Concn.	
g/100 c.c.	=o.	o-c.		=c.	o'-c.	=o'.	g/100 c.c.
0.4000	417.5°	+1.0°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±416.5°	-0.6°	415.9°	0.4040
	383.8	-0.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	384.6	-0.9	383.7	
	331.3	+0.8	Hg ₅₄₆₁	330.5	±0	330.5	
	278.8	+0.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	278.2	+0.3	278.5	
	263.8	+1.0	Na ₅₈₉₃	262.8	-0.5	262.3	
	237.5	-0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	237.9	+1.0	238.9	
	206.3	+0.9	Cd ₆₄₃₈	205.4	±0	205.4	
	182.5	-1.7	Li ₆₇₀₈	184.2	-1.0	183.2	

The solution exhibited slight mutarotation,

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